

Effect of High Commitment Human Resource Management Practices on Employees' Work-life Balance in the Banking Industry of Bangladesh

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between high commitment human resource management (HCHRM) practices and employees work-life (WLB) balance in the banking sector of Bangladesh. This study identifies five HRM practices as HCHRM. HCHRM is regarded as a multidimensional independent variable, whereas WLB is viewed as a dependent variable. Previous research indicated that High Commitment Human Resource Management (HCHRM) serves as a predictor of workers' work-life balance (WLB) in organizations that implement commitment-based HRM practices. Furthermore, research on HCHRM and employees' work-life balance (WLB) in Bangladesh is very underexplored. A total of 87 questionnaires were obtained from frontline staff across various banking organizations, with a response rate of 50.87%. SPSS VERSION 25, a first-generation statistical software, was utilized to assess reliability, validity, and hypotheses. The present study posited five hypotheses regarding the relationship between HCHRM (recruitment and selection, training, performance appraisal, compensation, and job design) and WLB. The analytical results indicated that four out of the five components of HCHRM significantly positively influence work-life balance (WLB). The data and existing literature indicate that HCHRM significantly affects employees' work-life balance (WLB), which in turn impacts organizational success. It is recommended that the management and authority of the organization incorporate high commitment human resource management (HCHRM) into the overall business strategy and implement practices that enhance employees' (WLB) to achieve sustainable competitive advantage through human resources.

Keywords

Work Life Balance, High Commitment HRM, Banking Industry, Sustainable Competitive Advantage.

1. Introduction

In the world of business, it is essential for the organizations to be updated in developing their strategies and implementing those strategies for attaining competitive edge in the industry. Therefore, it is the responsibility of the organization to focus on organizing necessary resources and their proper utilization where human resources can play a vital role. One important adaptation required for organizations is to make adjustment with their human resource practices to optimize their human resource. Thus, it is essential for the organizations to emphasize on different strategies where High Commitment Human Resource Management (HCHRM) has been adopted as “a group of separate but interconnected HR practices designed to enhance employees’ skills, knowledge and efforts” (Takeuchi et al., 2007). Organizations must take into account the work-life balance of employees, as globalization, intense competition, emerging technologies, and cross-cultural diversity have imposed significant burdens on the workforce. This adversely impacts on the health and well-being of the workforce. This leads to elevated production costs for the business (MacDonald, 2005).

Despite the extensive research on the impact of High-Commitment Human Resource Management (HCHRM) on organizational effectiveness, it is regrettable that significantly less empirical investigation has concentrated on HCHRM's influence on employees' WLB. Numerous prior researchers have indicated that a significant reason for the gap in studies is the over-reliance on data obtained from managerial responses, with insufficient attention to employee-level outcomes (Gould-Williams, 2004; Harley et al., 2007; Sparham & Sung, 2007). Alternative scholars have examined employee-level outcomes as "mediating variables" instead of outcome measures (Barling et al., 2003; Guest & Conway, 2007; Gong et al., 2009). These two aspects have partially contributed to a limited comprehension of the exact impact of HCHRM on employees' WLB. In the national context, although there have been few studies on work-life balance, no research has been undertaken on the impact of HCHRM on work-life balance. A potential reason for this disparity may be the insufficient awareness of the issue. Nawaz and Zaman (2012) discovered that most employees in the private banking sector lack familiarity with the notion of work-life balance, since 50% of the examined banks do not implement any WLB policies. This study paper investigates the impact of HCHRM practices on WLB within the banking sector of Bangladesh.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Banking Industry of Bangladesh

Bangladesh's economy has been expanding gradually and as a result, needs the assistance of a financial system. According to Alam et al. (2011), Bangladesh's banking sector has historically led the country's financial system. All commercial banks have been split into three generations based on when they were founded. After the country's liberation, the Bangladeshi government nationalized the entire local banking system through Presidential Order No. 26, known as the Bangladesh Banks Nationalization Order of 1972. Later, the government moved forward with restructuring and rebranding the banks to meet new objectives. It was permissible for foreign-owned banks to carry on operating in Bangladesh. Bangladesh was born into an interest-based financial system that had been established earlier when it was a British Colony. Since its start, Bangladesh has witnessed a fresh development in domestic and international banking. Bangladesh's banking industry is unique compared to those of other developed nations. Islamic banking is one of the major categories of scheduled banks that make up Bangladesh's banking service industry.

The banking sector constitutes the largest segment of Bangladesh's capital market (Sobhani, 2011). The significance of Bangladesh's banking sector is increasing daily due to favourable trends in remittances, garment exports, and foreign currency reserves. Sharmeen et al. (2013) indicate that the Government of Bangladesh has significantly invested through specialised banks to enhance agricultural development and has strategically sought additional finance from external entities such as the IMF. A substantial fraction of this credit is allocated as loans to destitute farmers and for the acquisition of vital input resources such as seeds, irrigation, and fertilisers. In addition to the government, several other

organisations (NGOs, MFIs, PCBs, FCBs, etc.) are encouraged to provide these farmers with access to their lending programs. The extensive agricultural sectors have had consistent, upward growth in recent years, and their contribution to GDP is substantial.

2.2 Work-life Balance

The work-life balance (WLB) has emerged as a significant concern for academicians, individuals, and organisations worldwide because of changing economic patterns, demographic shifts, technological advancements, and competitive factors (Baral & Bhargava, 2011). Furthermore, empirical studies that investigate the balance between work and family obligations frequently fail to distinguish between the various concepts that are present in the work (Rabby et al., 2023; Greenhaus et al., 2006). The expression "work-life balance" is contentious due to its implication that work is not essential to life and that there is only a straightforward trade-off between the two domains. This promotes the implementation of expedited solutions that fail to address fundamental disparities and transfers the responsibility for achieving a corresponding stability between work and personal life to individuals (Gregory & Milner, 2009).

Greenhaus (2002) defined WLB as the ability to function effectively and enjoy pleasure in both professional and personal environments with minimal role conflict. "Work-life balance" is the term used by Felstead et al. (2002) to describe the connection between organizational and cultural periods, as well as the places of work and non-work in countries where income is primarily earned and dispersed through labour markets. Aycaan et al. (2007) approached the concept of "life balance" from a more comprehensive perspective; however, they limited their discussion to the areas of employment and family. White et al. (2003) define WLB as the satisfaction of the demands of one's personal, family, and professional lives. labour requires the commitment of long hours, hard labour, and most of one's time.

2.3 High Commitment Human Resource Management (HCHRM)

HR practices and systems can be classified as either control-based or commitment-based HRM. In contrast to control-focused HR practices, which aim to reduce labour expenses and enhance efficiency, commitment-focused HR policies are designed to enhance employee commitment and enhance organisational performance (Whitener, 2001). Scholars have employed the HCHRM approach to characterise HRM that is commitment-oriented; however, their definitions of HCHRM are inconsistent. In addition, Whitener (2001) observed HRM strategies, including a high commitment approach to encouraging and committing employees, comprehensive training, internal and externally equitable incentive systems, developmental evaluation, and selected employment. HCHRM encompasses a variety of procedures, such as group incentives and skill-based compensation, cross-functional teams, extensive training, information exchange, and democratic processes, as well as strict selection grievance procedures and internal merit-based promotions (Datta et al., 2005). An HCHRM system is contingent upon procedures for compensation, comprehensive training, and selected employment, as per Lepak et al. (2006) maximizing the prospective contributions of employees to the organization's performance, encouraging employee loyalty, and rewarding performance. High-commitment HRM is a high-performance work system that aims to establish an affective connection between the organisation and the employee in order to ensure that workers are dedicated to organisational objectives (Lepak & Snell, 2002; Rabby et al., 2024). HCHRM systems achieve this by establishing enduring, dependable partnerships that communicate to employees the organization's dedication to meeting their requirements.

The most effective method of evaluating the outcomes of HRM practices is to evaluate their integrated impact, rather than by the specific practices themselves. High-commitment HRM is a collection of HR practices that unite the needs of employees and foster long-term commitment in return (Walton, 1985). However, the literature has shown that the specific practices that make up this collection tend to vary to a certain extent. Researchers Becker and Gerhart (1996) and Collins & Smith (2006) have identified these HR practices as having the potential to enhance the motivation, satisfaction, and performance of

employees, thereby enhancing the efficacy of an organisation. This study concentrates on the HCHRM system, which has been demonstrated to be effective in influencing employees' perceptions of balance through five HR practices: training, performance appraisal, recruitment and selection, compensation, and job design. This is due to our interest in WLB as a critical HRM outcome. Boon & Kalshoven (2014) previously recognized the HCHRM scale, which has been incorporated into these five practices.

3. Research Framework and Hypotheses Development

3.1 Research Framework

The current research is being conducted to find the impact of high-commitment HRM practices on the work-life balance of employees in the financial industry of Bangladesh. Five dimensions are examined in this study to elucidate high-commitment HRM practices: recruitment and selection, training, performance appraisal, rewards, and job design. Conversely, the dependent variable is work-life balance.

Fig. 1. Research framework of the current study

3.2 Hypothesis Development

Relationship between high commitment HRM and employees' work-life balance

In the current era of intense competition, it is imperative for organizations to prioritize employee work-life balance in order to stay afloat. This viewpoint is endorsed and verified by researchers. Concentrating on employees' WLB is substantially linked with enhanced organizational performance, as per the researchers. Currie, 2001; Schuster, 1998; Johnson et al., 2020). Thus, it is incumbent upon all organizations to guarantee that their employees maintain a healthy work-life balance. Various dimensions are identified by researchers as forecasters of employee work-life balance. For example, Zhang et al. (2022) demonstrate that organizations may implement high-commitment HRM practices as a way to improve the well-being of their employees. Zhang and his colleagues investigate the aspects of employee wellbeing, formal and informal relationships, and high-commitment HRM in the context of China. A substantial positive correlation between employee wellbeing and high-commitment HRM is discovered in the study's findings. Previous research has consistently shown that there are positive correlations between commitment to an organization and factors that influence employees' WLB, such as overall physical well-being (Siu et al., 1998), mental health (Grawitch et al., 2007), job-related well-

being (Aujla & Mclarney, 2020), and life satisfaction (Lu et al., 2009). As a result of the preceding literature, it is reasonable to assume that high-commitment HRM would improve the WLB of employees. Consequently, the current investigation can formulate the subsequent hypothesis that is supported by the literature.

Relationship between recruitment and selection, and work-life balance

Recruitment and selection process helps organization attract and identify the appropriate person for the job (Kumari & Malhotra, 2013). Setting the right expectations for candidates and not overpromising the benefits or underplaying the hardships of the job in recruitment communication effect employee perception of wellbeing and workload (Rasmussen, 2020). Overpromising in the recruitment communication and under delivering in the actual job could contribute to early burnout in employees (Spence et al., 2009; Kabir & Rabby, 2023). Ensuring the right person-organization and person-job fit during the selection process increases job satisfaction which in turn contributes to commitment and wellbeing (Lopes, 2020). The authors suggest that focusing on recruitment and selection practices to increase commitment could enhance the employee perception of wellbeing, balance, and satisfaction. Therefore, established on the previous literature review and the current research framework it can be revealed that to increase the WLB of employees' recruitment and selection policies should be developed accordingly. Thus, the following hypothesis can be considered for the current research.

H1: *Recruitment and selection have positive relationship with employees' work-life balance.*

Relationship between training and work-life balance

Tarafdar et al. (2007) found that most faculty members who are new to the university say they often feel overwhelmed by their responsibilities and unclear expectations. He concluded that work life stress is brought on by causes such as new job requirements, more challenging professional lives and regularly changing assignments. Rees and Redfern (2000) suggest that extensive training programs can be effective to reduce stress. Training on emotional intelligence reduces work related stress and positively affects employee health and job performance (Slaski & Cartwright, 2003; Imtiaz et al., 2024). In a recent study, Pingo et al. (2020) found that acceptance and commitment trainings alleviate work stress and increase job satisfaction by enhancing the effects of performance feedback. These authors suggest that extensive training programs might relieve work related stress by enabling employees to work more efficiently and to better understand work situations. Therefore, as per the previous literature review and the current research framework it can be revealed that to improve the WLB of employees' training programs might play an effective role. Thus, the following hypothesis can be considered for the current research.

H2: *Training has positive relationship with employees' work-life balance.*

Relationship between performance appraisal and work-life balance

Siegrist (2002) discovered that employees' mental health was adversely affected by an imbalance in effort and reward. Kinman and Jones (2008) have identified effort-reward imbalance as one of the factors contributing to work-related tension among employees. The employees of an organization's low impartiality perception of the performance appraisal procedure is the cause of the perception of effort-reward imbalance among employees (Getnet et al., 2014). The impartial perception of appraisal among employees is enhanced by their perceived system knowledge of appraisal and their participation (Kartikadewi et al., 2018). Additionally, Ryu and Hong (2020) note that constructive performance feedback enhances employees' dedication to the organization and their observation of the appraisal system as fair. A developmental appraisal that emphasizes feedback and employee development, in conjunction with a participative appraisal that equips employees with an understanding of the system's operation, may enhance their commitment and impartiality insights of the appraisal system. This would subsequently alleviate the reward imbalance and work-related tension. Consequently, the current

research framework and the previous literature review indicate that performance appraisals may contribute to the development of employees' work-life balance. Consequently, the hypothesis that follows is a viable option for the current investigation.

H3: *Performance appraisal has positive relationship with employees' work-life balance.*

Relationship between compensation and work-life balance

Compensation management is the process of evolving and putting into practice techniques to appropriately compensate personnel with the target of attracting, motivating, and retaining those people who are supposed to make it easier to achieve organizational goals (Dulebohn and Werling, 2007). Roehling and Moen (2001) have predicted that earnings are negatively correlated with work-life strain. Additionally, they discovered that a spouse with an volatile or small income places financial responsibility on the other companion, resulting in stress. The absence of a well-designed reward scheme may result in the perception that employees' efforts are more important than the benefits, which can lead to overworking and increase work-life strain (Steptoe et al., 2004; Preckel et al., 2007; Kinman & Jones, 2008; Giuseppe et al., 2024). In their investigation of the Malaysian event industry, Nizam and Kam (2018) discovered that the compensation scheme was positively correlated with work-life balance. These authors propose that employees' work-life equilibrium could be enhanced through the implementation of a comprehensive reward scheme. Consequently, the current research framework and the previous literature review indicate that compensation practices may contribute to the advancement of employees' work-life balance. Consequently, the hypothesis that follows is a viable option for the current investigation.

H4: *Compensation has positive relationship with employees' work-life balance.*

Relationship between job design and work-life balance

The Hackman and Lawler (1971) approach is the most extensively researched and accepted job approach to this day. Autonomy is one of the five fundamental job characteristics that are expected to impact an employee's inner work motivation. Autonomy is the point to which the job provides the employee with significant freedom. This investigation concentrates on this aspect of job design in order to illustrate its influence on work-life equilibrium. Flexibility of work schedule and Employee autonomy are strong predictors of WLB (Kinman and Jones, 2008). Work schedule rigidity, according to Rabby (2024), increased physical suffering such insomnia, eating issues, and aches and pains associated with tension. It also raised depression in both men and women. According to Ramakrishnan and Arokiasamy (2019), flextime programs resulted in decreased attrition, absenteeism, and tardiness. Shagvaliyeva and Yazdanifard (2014) found that flexible scheduling policies improved employee productivity by reducing absenteeism and turnover, and they benefited families by reducing employee melancholy, as families had more time together and there was less friction between work and family. A primary predictor of work-life concord. Parasuraman and Simmers (2001) noted that individuals can reduce the likelihood of work-family conflict by scheduling work to a greater extent when they have autonomy in their work. These authors propose that employees' WLB may be enhanced by a job design that priorities employee autonomy and a flexible schedule. Therefore, the current research framework and the previous literature review indicate that job design may contribute to the improvement of employees' work-life balance. Consequently, the hypothesis that follows is a viable option for the current investigation.

H5: *Job design has positive relationship with employees' work-life balance.*

4. Methodology

Research Design

Creswell (2009) defines research design as a methodical approach to selecting between competing hypotheses by collecting and analysing data. This investigation is a cross-sectional investigation that was conducted from July 2023 to September 2024. The data was accumulated, and the conclusions were derived after conducting the research. Furthermore, the present investigation is classified as a correlational study since all pertinent data were collected in accordance with the theoretical framework (Cooper and Schindler, 2008). This study utilized the supervisors' perspectives regarding the diverse components of high commitment HRM and work-life balance. The questionnaire survey was the primary source of measurement in the current investigation. Salkind (2006) recommended that the questionnaire survey method be employed to investigate the correlation between various variable quantity in social science research.

Population, Sample and Unit of Analysis

Population is the term used to describe the entire collection of subjects or events that are being investigated (Sekaran & Bougie, 2010). In order to mitigate errors in sample selection, it is imperative that each research endeavour specify its target population (Cavana et al., 2001). The target demographic of the study is all front-level financiers in Bangladesh's banking industry, including assistant officers, different trainee assistant officers, entry level trainee assistant cash officers, and equivalent officials, who account for the majority of the survey responses. Front-level financiers are considered the most critical human resource in this industry due to their substantial presence in the workforce. Consequently, they are the valid sample respondents for the current study.

A total of 61 banking organizations were registered in Bangladesh. The sample size should be at least ten times the number of variables proposed in the research, or a larger number, as per Sekaran and Bougie (2010). Consequently, in accordance with this guideline, the minimum sample size for the current investigation is 60 (6*10) or greater. The convenience sampling method, a non-probability sampling method, was used in the current study. This method involves selecting a sample from the population segment that is most readily accessible. The most frequently cited justification for implementing convenience

Sampling offers the advantage of being more cost-effective than probability sampling and can often be completed more quickly. Battaglia (2008) noted that convenience sampling is based on the assumption that the target population is homogeneous. This implies that the results obtained from a convenience sample would be the same as those from a random sample, a locally sourced sample, a cooperative sample, or even a sample from a hard-to-reach segment of the population. The nature of the work for front-line financiers is relatively consistent across organizations due to the highly regulated pastry industry in Bangladesh. As a result, the population of the present study is homogeneous and meets the criteria for convenience sampling.

Research Instrument

The measurement instrument employed in the present investigation is detailed in this section. The questionnaire comprises three sections. Part A consists of 15 items that assess five-dimensional high commitment HRM practices, including recruitment and selection, training, performance appraisal, compensation, and job design. The five-item WLB scale is detailed in Part B. Finally, part C furnishes the respondent's demographic info, including age, gender, marital status, experience, and monthly income.

Table 1: Research Measurement Instrument

Variables	Constructs	Items	Sources
High commitment HRM (HCHRM)	Recruitment and Selection	3	Boon and Kalshoven (2014)
	Training	3	Boon and Kalshoven (2014)
	Performance Appraisal	3	Boon and Kalshoven (2014)
	Compensation	3	Boon and Kalshoven (2014)
	Job Design	3	Boon and Kalshoven (2014)
Work-life Balance		5	Brough et al. (2009)
Demographic Variables	Age, Gender, Marital Status, Experience, Monthly Income	5	
Total		25	

High Commitment HRM (HCHRM)

In this research 5 dimensions were used to explain high commitment HRM (HCHRM) practices such as recruitment and selection, training, performance appraisal, compensation, and job design. In total 15 items were used to measure HCHRM (3 items for recruitment and selection, 3 for training, 3 for appraisal, 3 for compensation and another 3 for job design). These 15 items high commitment HRM (HCHRM) practices were adapted from previous work of Boon and Kalshoven (2014).

Work-life Balance

A total of 5 items were employed for measuring work-life balance. This 5 items scale was adapted from the work of Brough et al. (2009).

Demographic Information

Yiing and Ahmad (2009) have observed that demographics have an effect on organizational responses as well as behavior constructs. Based on this issue, numerous questions with regards to respondents' demographic information were included in the questionnaire. Five demographic variables applied in the current study were (a) age, (b) gender, (c) marital status, (d) experience, and (e) monthly income.

Reliability of Scale

The scale's internal consistency and reliability were examined using Nunnally and Bernstein's (1994) recommendations. Version 25 of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was used to examine

the current study's scale's reliability. Internal reliability in the current study was 0.872, higher than the suggested minimum of 0.6. The scale's Cronbach Alpha is summarized in the following Table 5.2.

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha of Score

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.872	6

Data Collection Procedures

The human resource departments of 26 banks were contacted verbally and by email during the first phase of the data collection procedure to obtain a list of the email addresses of their front-level bankers. A succinct description of the study's objectives, the methods for distributing the questionnaire, and the email data collection from their staff are all included in the request letter. Ten organizations consented to participate in the data collection process after the researcher reached out to 26 banking institutions. For this purpose, the researcher gathered 171 front-level banker email addresses from 10 different institutions. Each of these 171 email addresses received an email with the questionnaire link and details about the study's goals and methodology. Mertler (2002) talked about the advantages of communicating directly with sample population members via email. The researcher can assess the response rate and potentially boost confidence in the generalizability of the research findings by promoting an online survey and encouraging participation via email.

Data Preparation

Before starting the data analysis, it is essential for the research to check accuracy in the data set. By employing SPSS 22.0 version, the researcher checked the frequencies of all the individual variables and the scores that were out of range or not. Furthermore, after checking the error in the data set the researcher searched for the missing values.

Common Method Variance (CMV)/ Bias

When utilizing a group with only one respondent, CMV is more likely to cause issues. The measurement method's issue is linked to CMV (Podsakoff et al., 2003). Overstated convergent validity is produced by Common Method Variance CMV (Carlson et al., 2012). This work employed the proximal parting technique (Podsakoff et al. 2003) to counteract Common Method Variance CMV. Different sets of measuring items are included in the questioner, along with instructions for each build that appear individually.

Data Analysis

For data analysis and hypotheses testing numerous tools and techniques were employed in the current study. For instance, for data inserting and descriptive analysis statistical package for Social Science (SPSS-Version 25) was used.

5. Findings And Analysis

This section presents the findings from the data analysis as well as the study's hypothesis. The analysis begins with descriptive statistics for the variables used in the study and an overview of the respondents' demographic profiles. Additionally, common method bias was assessed and reported using Harman's single-factor analysis.

Response Rate

The characteristics of the respondents in the current study is made clear in Table 3. Front-line bankers in Bangladesh's banking sector were the study's target respondents. Through the HR department of the banking organizations, 298 questionnaires were delivered to the respondents in total. The respondents were asked to complete the surveys within a week. Out of 171 surveys, 87 were returned, for a 50.87 percent response rate. Leslie (1972) asserts that surveys of homogeneous populations (those with a strong sense of group identity) about their attitudes, opinions, viewpoints, etc. towards issues related to the inquiry are unlikely to exhibit considerable response-rate bias. As a result, the current study's 50.87 percent response rate is suitable for data analysis and interpretation.

Table 3: Response Rate

Questionnaire	Number	Percentage
Total Distributed Questionnaires	171	100
Total Returned Questionnaires	87	50.87
Total Non-returned Questionnaires	84	49.13
Usable Questionnaires	87	50.87
Unusable Questionnaires	0	0

Profile of the Respondents

Using the SPSS software 20.0 version, Table 4 shows a summary of the respondent profile for the study. Between the ages of 24 and 30, 50.6% of the respondents are in this age range. However, just 8% of those surveyed are between the ages of 41 and 45. Gender-wise, 32.2 percent of the respondents are female, and over three-fifths (62.1%) are male. Married people made up the majority of responders (67.8%). Regarding experience, around 80 percent have one to six years of experience.

Table 4: Descriptive Analysis of the Demographic Data

Demographic Data	Frequency (N= 87)	Percentage (%)
Age:		
24-30 Years	44	50.6
31-40 Years	36	41.4

41-45 Years	7	8.0
Gender:		
Male	54	62.1
Female	33	37.9
Marital Status:		
Married	59	67.8
Unmarried	28	32.2
Income:		
Tk. 41,000 - Tk.50,000	31	35.6
Tk. 36,000 - Tk. 40,000	26	29.9
Above Tk. 50,000	22	25.3
Tk. 28,000 - Tk. 35,000	8	9.2
Experience:		
1-3 Years	38	43.7
4-6 Years	37	42.5
7-10 Years	8	9.2
Above 10 Years	4	4.6

Bias and Common Method Variance (CMV)

There is a possibility of CMV even if the data used in this study came from specific source (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The subsequent procedures were used in the current study to reduce the CMV: (i) When creating the questionnaire, the study used the proximal separation strategy. (ii) To control the amount of variance explained by the factors, the Harman single factor test was employed. According to the outcomes of the Harman single factor analysis, six factors explained 68.45% of the variation, with the first factor explaining 27.25%, or less than 50%. Thus, the current study demonstrates that CMV is not a significant issue based on the analytical results and the literature support.

Descriptive Statistics

The study variables' maximum, minimum, mean, and standard deviation are displayed in Table 5. A 5-point Likert scale was used to measure the independent and dependent variables. Where the mean value for every construct was determined to be higher than 3.0. For example, WLB had the highest standard deviation (0.98), and compensation had the highest mean (3.73).

Table 5: Descriptive statistics of the Latent Constructs

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Recruitment and Selection	87	1.00	5.00	3.49	.949
Training	87	1.00	5.00	3.39	.905
Performance Appraisal	87	1.00	5.00	3.46	.909
Compensation	87	2.00	5.00	3.73	.772
Job Design	87	1.00	5.00	3.24	.935
Work-life Balance	87	1.00	5.00	3.46	.989

Results of the Correlation Analysis

Table 6 summarizes the outcomes of the correlation analysis. All dimensions of the independent variable are positively correlated with the dependent variable at 99 percent confidence interval.

Table 6: Correlation Analysis

Correlations							
		RS	TR	PA	CM	JD	WLB
RS	Pearson Correlation	1	.962**	.957**	.823**	.905**	.948**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	N	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0
TR	Pearson Correlation	.962**	1	.946**	.808**	.906**	.939**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	N	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0

PA	Pearson Correlation	.957**	.946**	1	.766**	.867**	.912**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00	0.00
	N	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0
CM	Pearson Correlation	.823**	.808**	.766**	1	.793**	.834**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00	0.00
	N	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0
JD	Pearson Correlation	.905**	.906**	.867**	.793**	1	.912**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		0.00
	N	87	87	87	87	87	87
WLB	Pearson Correlation	.948**	.939**	.912**	.834**	.912**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
	N	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0	87.0
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).							

Output of Regression Analysis

The basic and important criteria for a model is the coefficient of resolve (R^2), and the beta value that is called the level of path coefficients (Chin, 2010; Hair et al., 2019). The main objective is to attain the higher R^2 . Cohen (1988) suggested different landmark for the R square value such as 0.02-0.12 specifies weak, 0.13-0.25 is restrained and 0.26 to above is substantial. R square value explains the relationship among the variables based on the hypotheses. This is indicated by beta coefficient (R^2). For assessing the path model, a bootstrap analysis with 1000 resampling was employed based on the guidelines of Hair et al. (2019). Result of the analysis showed the R^2 value significant and accepted according to the guideline of Cohen (1988). In this study the R^2 value found 72.30% for work-life balance. Therefore, the explained variance of all WLB was found substantial which means that high commitment HRM (HCHRM) is a considerable predictor of work-life balance.

Table 7: Regression Output

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.711 ^a	.723	.720	.222

a. Predictors: (Constant), JD, CM, PA, TR, RS

Results of the Hypotheses Analysis

Table 8 summarizes the results of the direct hypotheses analysis. Based on the analysis, the results indicate significant and positive relationship between four of the five dimensions of high commitment HRM (HCHRM) in this study and WLB. There was no significant positive relationship found between performance appraisal and WLB.

Table 8: Results of Direct Hypotheses Test

Direct Hypotheses	Std. Beta	Std. Error	t-Value	P Value	Decision
Recruitment and Selection > Work-life Balance	.415	.152	2.85**	.005	Supported
Training > Work-life Balance	.229	.138	1.81*	.074	Supported
Performance Appraisal > Work-life Balance	.014	.125	.121	.904	Not Supported
Compensation > Work-life Balance	.122	.072	2.16**	.033	Supported
Job Design > Work-life Balance	.220	.082	2.83**	.006	Supported

Note: **p < 0.05, * p <0.10, (based on One-tailed test with 1000 bootstrapping)

6. Discussion

The current study looked at the relationship between employees' WLB and high commitment HRM (HCHRM) practices, which include hiring and selection, training, performance reviews, pay, and job design. With five dimensions, HCHRM was regarded as the independent variable in this investigation. Conversely, WLB was used as an outcome variable or dependent variable. In the current study, a total of five direct hypotheses between independent and dependent variables were developed. Of the five possibilities, four were deemed noteworthy.

The current study's first hypothesis examined how hiring and selection procedures affected workers' WLB in Bangladesh's banking sector. Based on the analysis's conclusions, it was discovered that hiring and selection procedures significantly improved workers' work-life balance. The earlier research supports the current conclusions (Rasmussen, 2020; Lopes, 2020). These authors found that emphasizing commitment-based hiring and selection procedures improves workers' perceptions of balance, happiness, and well-being. According to the current research, hiring and selection procedures are likely to have a significant positive impact on the WLB of employees in Bangladesh's banking sector.

The study's second hypothesis examined how training affected workers' WLB in Bangladesh's banking sector. Training was determined to significantly improve employees' WLB based on the analysis's findings. The results of this study are consistent with those of other researchers (Pingo et al., 2020).

According to these writers, comprehensive training programs may improve employees' WLB by empowering them to perform more productively and comprehend job-related circumstances. Employees would experience less stress at work as a result, and work and personal circumstances would become more balanced. It may be inferred from the current research that training positively affects workers' work-life balance.

Examining the impact of performance reviews on workers' work-life balance in Bangladesh's banking sector was the third hypothesis of the current study. The study's conclusions did not indicate that performance review procedures significantly improved work-life balance. The present results contradict those of earlier studies conducted by other researchers (Getnet et al., 2014; Ryu & Hong, 2020). These authors claim that a participative evaluation that gives staff members insight into the system's operation together with constructive criticism helps them maintain a healthy work-life balance. Nevertheless, both investigations were carried out in industrialised nations. Many Bangladeshi organisations, especially banks, may not maintain the same appraisal standards as those studies suggest. In Bangladesh, many organisations still perform their appraisals solely using the supervisor's judgement without providing developmental comments. Additionally, employees cannot see through appraisal systems (Hossain & Farhana, 2012). These may be the likely reason why, in the case of the banking sector in Bangladesh, no meaningfully positive correlation between WLB and performance reviews was found.

Another objective of the current study was to explore the effect of compensation practices on employees' work-life balance in the banking industry of Bangladesh. The finding of the research showed significant positive influences of compensation practices on work-life balance. The current study finding is consistent with earlier research (Nizam & Kam, 2018). These authors found that an extensive compensation package scheme improved the perception of WLB of employees by making their effort seem more justified. Employees perceive their time and energy to be well spent when it is well compensated by the organization which leads to more satisfaction both towards work and life as whole. Therefore, based on the findings of the analysis the current research reveals that employees feel extensive compensation practices would equip them better to handle work strain, contributing to a better work-life balance.

Examining the impact of job design on workers' work-life balance in Bangladesh's banking sector was the final hypothesis of the current study. The analysis's findings indicated a strong positive correlation between job design and workers' work-life balance. Previous study (Shagvaliyeva & Yazdanifard, 2014; Ramakrishnan & Arokiasamy, 2019) supports the current findings. These authors discovered that a job design that prioritises employee autonomy and flexible scheduling enhances workers' work-life balance. Because it enables employees to manage resources like time and effort on their own terms, job design has the greatest impact on employees' WLB among HR approaches. Thus, it is clear that WLB and job design are related.

7. Implications

Theoretical Implications

High-commitment HRM seeks to forge an emotional bond between employees and the organisation by developing enduring, reliable partnerships that demonstrate the organization's prioritisation of resolving employee needs (Boon & Kalshoven, 2014). The present research identifies the influence of HCHRM on WLB through recruiting and selection, employee training, periodical performance appraisal, regular compensation, and job design. This research contributes significantly to the field of WLB by incorporating HCHRM as a pivotal factor. Much of the preceding material employs wellbeing or contentment as a consequence of HCHRM. This study examines the impact of several aspects of High Commitment Human Resource Management (HCHRM) practices on employees' WLB. The study is crucial for obtaining significant insights into the elements of High Commitment Human Resource

Management (HCHRM) and the outcomes it yields for organisations regarding WLB concerns. This study elucidates the concepts of High Commitment HRM and WLB within the context of Bangladesh, a developing nation requiring such evidence, as well as from the standpoint of the banking business. Finally, Baral and Bhargava (2011) suggested that it would be prudent to undertake a study on the enhancement of work and family dynamics in the subcontinent. Family serves as a social institution in the subcontinent, providing both emotional support and assistance during challenging periods. This study contributes to the literature on employee WLB from a subcontinental perspective, distinguishing it from a Western viewpoint.

Practical Implications

Additionally, the theoretical contributions can be illustrated with a multitude of practical implications for the decision-makers and practitioners of organizations. The significance of HRM aspects in the WLB issues of employees could be attributed to practitioners and decision makers. Additionally, organizations may foster the WLB of their employees by promoting HCHRM. Significant positive impacts on employees' WLB are demonstrated by the analysis' findings, which pertain to four dimensions of HCHRM: recruitment and selection, training, compensation, and job design. Consequently, it implies that organizations should prioritize commitment-based HRM practices in order to achieve a WLB for their employees. The management of the organization will gain an understanding of the various dimensions of HCHRM and how they will be integrated into the HR policies of the organization. Moreover, in a specific context, the significance of commitment-based recruitment and selection practices for the banking organization can be understood by decision makers. Subsequently, they may determine how to cultivate these employees through training that is based on commitment. In order to facilitate the work-life equilibrium of employees, compensation policies and job design could be tailored accordingly. It can be inferred that organizations should prioritize HCHRM practices in order to enhance the WLB of their employees, thereby contributing to their competitive advantage by developing more productive employees.

Conclusion

The current research has substantially acknowledged the significance of work-life balance. Consequently, high-commitment HRM strategies are acknowledged as a means of improving the performance of organizations by improving the WLB capabilities of employees. The financial industry in Bangladesh is the context in which such evidence is discovered. HCHRM constructions are comprised of five dimensions. Conversely, the dependent variable was WLB. Between the independent and dependent variables, five hypotheses are identified. The current research indicates that the WLB of employees is significantly influenced by the four dimensions of HCHRM (recruitment and selection, training, compensation, and job design). The research specifies that organizations must comprehend and recognize the importance of HCHRM practices in order to maintain the WLB of their employees, as indicated by the findings of the current study and the previous literature. In summary, it is imperative for organizations to emphasize the significance of HCHRM practices and implement them effectively in order to achieve WLB for employees and a sustained competitive advantage through human resources.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data is available upon request from researchers who meet the eligibility criteria.

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